

COMPARATIVE STUDIES OF DIFFERENT METHODS FOR EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF PREGNANCY BASED ON DETERMINATION OF PROGESTERONE LEVELS AND PAG IN BUFFALOES OF THE BULGARIAN MURRA BREED

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to perform a comparative evaluation of the methods for early diagnosis of pregnancy in buffalo cows of the Bulgarian Murrah breed by determining the concentrations of progesterone in serum, the P4 Rapid test in milk and the proteins associated with pregnancy in serum and milk. Blood samples were obtained from 57 buffalo cows, as well as 55 milk samples on the 23rd (progesterone determination in serum and milk) and 28th day (PAG determination in serum and milk) after artificial insemination. We interpreted the results of the rapid P4 test according to the manufacturer's instructions. Determination of serum concentrations of progesterone was performed with an ELISA analyzer Huma Reader (HUMAN, Germany), with a Progesterone EIA 96 TEST kit (Linear Chemicals, Spain). Pregnancy-specific glycoproteins were determined by the ELISA method using the Alertys Bovine Pregnancy kit for blood and milk. A transrectal ultrasound examination for pregnancy was performed on day 35 after insemination. The obtained results for the parameters characterizing the effectiveness of the methods used were processed by a computer statistical program (Statistica 7, Microsoft Corp. 1984-2000 Inc.) by a non-parametric method of percentage comparison. The highest sensitivity was recorded in the method for determining progesterone in serum, and the lowest in determining PAG in milk. For PAG ELISA tests, 100% specificity was found, while the other two tests had low values of 71.1% and 72.5%). The accuracy of individual methods for early diagnosis of pregnancy is in the range of 80.0% – 98.2%. Rapid P4 tests and serum progesterone distribution can be used to identify non-pregnant animals after insemination. PAG ELISA tests have high efficiency and are preferable to other methods for diagnosing early pregnancy in buffalo cows.

Key words: Pregnancy, P4 Rapid test, Progesterone, Pregnancy-associated glycoproteins, buffalo.

Introduction

Effective management of the reproductive process is a key issue in dairy farming. Lack of estrus, failed artificial insemination and non-application of methods for early diagnosis of pregnancy lead to significant financial losses.

Timely and accurate diagnosis of pregnancy in productive animals has the potential to improve reproductive performance by shortening the interval between births (Whitlock and Maxwell, 2008; Ott et al., 2014). Diagnosis of pregnancy in buffalo cows is mainly by rectal palpation or transrectal ultrasound, but these methods are accurate after day 45 of insemination (Arthur et al., 1996).

An ideal test for early diagnosis of pregnancy in dairy animals should meet the following criteria: high sensitivity (i.e. correctly identify pregnant animals), high specificity (i.e. correctly identify non-pregnant animals), be inexpensive and easily applicable under field conditions (Barbato et al., 2022).

Progesterone concentrations change during the individual phases of the sexual cycle and pregnancy. Their determination in blood serum or milk is an important practical method to improve the reproductive determination of buffaloes (Mehmedi et al., 2021). Progesterone test P4 Rapid test®

(Biocom-Trendaphilov Ltd) is a quick, easy and economical method for establishing low or high levels of progesterone in milk, based on the ELISA progesterone test and developed into a test strip.

Pregnancy-associated glycoproteins (PAGs) are one of the biomarkers for establishing pregnancy in ruminants. Expression starts during implantation and continues throughout pregnancy. Their determination allows a quick and accurate assessment of their reproductive status (Silva et al., 2007; Peter, 2013).

The aim of the present study was to perform a comparative evaluation of the methods for early diagnosis of pregnancy in buffalo cows of the Bulgarian Murrah breed by determining the concentrations of progesterone in serum, the P4 Rapid test in milk and the proteins associated with pregnancy in serum and milk.

Materials and methods

Animals

The study was carried out in 2021–2022 at a buffalo farm in Makak village, Shumen district. The study included 57 buffaloes over 60 days postpartum with applied synchronization protocols. The day on which artificial insemination was performed was taken as day 0.

Milk samples for examination with progesterone test Rapid P4

Milk samples were obtained at the morning milking on day 23 after artificial insemination. Fifty-five buffaloes were tested with progesterone test rapid P4. We interpreted the results of the rapid P4 test according to the instructions of the manufacturer, namely a positive diagnosis (one line - H +) and a negative (two lines - L -).

Blood samples for determination of progesterone concentrations in serum

To determine serum concentrations of P4, individual blood samples were obtained from v. jugularis after pre-fixation on day 23 after programmed artificial insemination.

For this purpose, 16G needles and a closed tube for serum (with beads) 16x75 mm, 10 ml (BIOSIGMA, Italy) were used. After transport to the laboratory, the blood was centrifuged at 3000 rpm. for 15 minutes and the separated serum was stored in sterile tubes (1.5 ml Ependorff), at a temperature of 0–200°C, until the analysis was carried out.

Determination of serum concentrations of progesterone was performed with an ELISA analyzer Huma Reader (HUMAN, Germany) using the Progesterone EIA 96 TEST kit (Linear Chemicals, Spain). The test is a competition-based "sandwich" ELISA for the quantification of progesterone in biological fluids. Enzyme activity was read photometrically at a wavelength of 450 nm on a Huma Reader (HUMAN, Germany). From the constructed standard curve with a sensitivity of 0.03–0.07 ng/ml, the optical densities of the tested samples were transformed into progesterone concentrations in ng/ml.

Blood and milk samples to determine glycoproteins associated with pregnancy

Blood samples were obtained on day 28 after artificial insemination from v. jugularis in 10-ml vacuum containers, allowed to clot at room temperature for 1 h before being refrigerated at 4–6°C for transport to the laboratory. Samples were centrifuged at 2000 × g for 10 min and the separated serum was stored at –20 °C.

Milk samples were obtained on day 28 after artificial insemination in 30-ml plastic containers at the morning milking. Samples were transported at 4–6°C and were examined within 1 h of arrival at the laboratory.

PAG concentrations in serum and milk were measured using commercial ELISA kits (IDEXX Laboratories, Inc., Westbrook, ME, USA). All analyzes were performed in the laboratory of the Department of Obstetrics, Reproduction and Reproductive Disorders of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine. The results of the ELISA assays were calculated as from the optical density (OD) of the sample corrected by subtracting the reference wavelength OD of the sample (S) minus the OD of the negative control (N) at 450 nm wavelength and both values are corrected subtracting the reference wavelength OD of the negative control) and obtaining the S-N value.

Pregnancy results were interpreted based on cutoff values determined by the PAG ELISA manufacturer. For the serum PAG ELISA, when the S-N value was < 0.300 , buffalo cows were classified as “not pregnant”; when the S-N value was > 0.300 and < 1.000 , they were classified as “retest” and when the S-N value was ≥ 1.000 , the animals were classified as “pregnant”. For PAG ELISA milk, when the S-N value was < 0.100 , buffalo cows were classified as “not pregnant”; when the S-N value was > 0.100 and < 0.250 recheck' and when the S-N value was ≥ 0.250 as 'pregnant'.

PAG ELISA test results were categorized as follows: correct diagnosis of pregnant (a); diagnosis pregnant incorrect (b); diagnosis not pregnant correct (c) and diagnosis not pregnant incorrect (d). From these values, sensitivity ($100 a/a + d$), specificity ($100 c/c + b$), accuracy ($100 (a + c) / (a + c + b + d)$), PPV ($100 a/a + b$) and NPV ($100 c/c + d$) of pregnancy diagnosis were calculated (Barbato et al., 2017).

To evaluate the results of the progesterone studies in milk and serum, as well as the serum and milk PAG ELISA tests in buffalo cows with unknown pregnancy status, a table was constructed to calculate indicators such as sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value (NPV) on days 23 and 28 and those based on transrectal ultrasonography performed on day 35 after artificial insemination.

Ultrasound diagnosis of pregnancy

Pregnancy was diagnosed using an ultrasound device, transrectal access, linear multifrequency probe 7–12 MHz on the 35th day after artificial insemination. Criteria for establishing pregnancy were an enlarged uterine lumen, visualization of the embryonic vesicle, and fetal heart rate as described by Fricke et al. (2016).

Research was conducted in compliance with Animal Welfare Regulations.

Statistical processing

The obtained data were processed using the computer statistical program StatSoft (Statistica 7, Microsoft Corp. 1984–2000, non-parametric analysis for the comparison of proportions. The results are presented as relative proportion (%) and confidence levels. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results

By means of the rapid P4 test in milk, 28 positive results and 27 negative ones were made. At day 35 ultrasound, 17 positive diagnoses were confirmed, as well as all 27 negative ones. Serum progesterone concentrations were above 1 ng/ml (positive for pregnancy) in 28 buffalo cows and below this value in 29 samples (negative for pregnancy). 17 of the positive diagnoses and 29 of the negative were subsequently confirmed. When determining PAG in milk, we received 14 positive diagnoses of pregnancy, 24 negative and 7 for re-examination. Positive and negative diagnoses were confirmed sonographically, and 3 buffalo cows from the recheck group were recorded as pregnant

and 4 were non-pregnant. The obtained PAG serum results were 17 positive for pregnancy and 40 negative, all of which were confirmed by ultrasound examination (Table 1).

Table 1: Results for early diagnosis of pregnancy in serum and milk from buffalo cows of the Bulgarian Murrah breed on the 23rd and 28th day after artificial insemination, depending on the method used.

	Positive (n)	Negative (n)	Second evaluation (n)	Confirmed pregnancy (n)	Confirmed non-pregnant (n)
Rapid P4 milk	28	27		17	27
Progesterone in serum	28	29		17	29
PAG milk	14	34	7	17	38
PAG serum	17	40		17	40

For the rapid milk progesterone test method (rapid P4), low values were reported in terms of positive predicted diagnoses (60.7%), specificity (71.1%), accuracy (80.0%), sensitivity and negative predicted diagnoses per 100 %.

The analysis of the obtained results regarding specificity, accuracy and positively predicted diagnoses based on obtained serum progesterone concentrations were in unsatisfactory limits 72.5%, 80.7% and 60.7%. Sensitivity criteria and negatively predicted diagnoses are in absolute values (Table 2).

Table 2: Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV) of the methods used for early diagnosis of pregnancy in buffalo cows of the Bulgarian Murrah breed. Adapted from Ricci et al., 2005.

	Sensitivity % (n/n)	Specificity % (n/n)	Volume % (n/n)	PPV % (n/n)	NPV % (n/n)
Rapid P4 milk	100 (17/17)	71,1 (27/38)**	80,0 (44/55)***	60,7(17/28)****	100 (27/27)
P4 serum	100 (17/17)	72,5 (29/40)**	80,7 (46/57)***	60,7(17/28)****	100 (29/29)
PAG serum	94,4 (17/18)	100 (41/41)	98,2 (56/57)	100 (17/17)	100 (41/41)
PAG milk	87,5 (14/16)*	100 (39/39)	96,4 (53/55)	100 (14/14)	95,1 (39/41)

Columns 1,2/4 $p < 0.0001^*$; 1/3,4 and 2/3,4 $p < 0.0002^{**}$; 1,,2/3,4 $p < 0.005^{***}$; 1,2/3,4 $p < 0.0022^{****}$

Sensitivity – the proportion of pregnant cows with a positive result of the applied method.

Specificity – the proportion of non-pregnant cows with a negative result of the applied method.

Volume – proportion of pregnancy status results, pregnant and non-pregnant, that were correctly classified by the method used.

PPV – the proportion of cows diagnosed as pregnant using the applied method that were actually pregnant.

NPV – fraction of cows diagnosed as non-pregnant using the applied method that were not really pregnant.

The sensitivity of the method for determining pregnancy-related proteins in the present study was within acceptable limits, 94.4% for the serum and 87.5% for the milk PAG ELISA test, respectively. Absolute values were recorded for the specificity of the PAG ELISA tests in buffalo serum and milk. The accuracy of serum and milk PAG ELISA tests on day 28 after artificial insemination of buffalo cows was 98.2% and 96.4%, respectively. The positive predictive value (PPV) rates for the serum and milk PAG ELISA tests were 100%, while the negative predictive value (NPV) rates were 95.1% and 100%, respectively (Table 2).

Discussion

Progesterone concentrations in milk or serum can be quantified using laboratory RIA or ELISA tests. Quality tests for the determination of progesterone in milk are commercially available. The advantages of these tests are that they can be carried out using a milk sample, which is easier for farm workers to obtain than a blood sample, and the test can be carried out on the farm rather than sent to a laboratory which requires time to return results. Commercial milk progesterone tests

are intended to be performed between days 18 and 24 after artificial insemination. A number of researchers have reported a specificity of 98% (Gowan et al., 1982; Pennington et al., 1985; Wimpy et al., 1985; Nebel et al., 1987) and have defined the method as the earliest possible to identify non-pregnant animals after breeding.

Our results support the thesis that the determination of progesterone in blood and milk has a lower degree of accuracy and is useful for identifying non-pregnant animals. Due to lower accuracy and specificity, Sambriddhi et al. (2019) do not recommend the progesterone ELISA to confirm a pregnancy diagnosis, but it can be used for screening purposes 21 days after insemination.

Detection of pregnancy by determining progesterone levels in serum or milk is 95% to 100% accurate (Rhodes, 2005). Using the P4 Rapid (Ridgeway Science, UK), 277 cows were determined positive for pregnancy on day 21, subsequently on day 60 by rectal examination, pregnancy was confirmed in 263 (Mehmedi et al., 2021). In contrast to these results, Purohit (2010) reported that the accuracy using a progesterone test between the 19th and 21st day post-insemination is usually around 80%, similar results were recorded by Chang and Estergreen (1983) in the range of 67.2 to 87.5%. Unsatisfactory accuracy in determining progesterone on day 21 after insemination was reported by Perera et al. (1980) and Arora et al. (1980) 66.7% and 75%, respectively. Kaul and Praska, (1980) reported accuracies in pregnancy diagnosis by milk progesterone determination of 57.1%, 69.5% and 75% on day 20, 22 and 24, respectively insemination. In our research, we found the results of using the two tests for early diagnosis of pregnancy in buffalo cows to be 81.8% and 80.4% accurate, respectively. Factors that may contribute to misdiagnosis are irregular cycles, early embryonic death, which varies from day 19 to 25 in buffaloes, the resulting uterine pathology, persistence of the corpus luteum, luteal cysts, incorrect timing of insemination, and embryonic death after the 24th day. Fricke et al. (2002) reported that 10 to 16% of cows diagnosed as pregnant on day 28 post-insemination experienced embryonic losses by day 56 post-artificial insemination.

For the determination of pregnancy-associated proteins (PAGs), regional laboratories are needed for quantification of PAGs by ELISA or RIA. Although this allows the quantification of serum PAG under laboratory conditions, this method leads to some fundamental difficulties. Inaccuracies are possible in the labeling and tracking of animal identification throughout the process from blood sampling to return of the information. Second, and more importantly, there is a 2-to-3-day turnaround time from blood sample collection to return of information to the farm. Currently, PAG-2 mRNA can be used for early diagnosis of pregnancy and embryonic death in buffalo cows, but the cost and impossibility of single samples is still a real problem (Barbato et al., 2022).

Isolation of PAGs from placenta allows development of the system for their determination (RIA 860) and improvement of accuracy for early diagnosis of pregnancy, reaching 99% on day 28 of artificial insemination (Barbato et al., 2017; Barbato et al., 2008). In our study, we found 98.2% accuracy in early pregnancy diagnosis by determining pregnancy-related proteins in serum and 96.4% in milk on the 28th week after insemination.

The sensitivity and specificity of the method based on determination of progesterone concentrations based on RIA in serum is 92.0% and 82.6% to 91.9%. Whereas, the sensitivity and specificity of PAG-1 pregnancy test based on radioimmunoassay of serum samples was 95.2% to 100.0% and 56.7% to 79.0%, on day 29-30 after artificial insemination (Szenci et al., 1998). PAG tests have been shown to be a reliable biomarker for early detection of pregnancy (Karen et al., 2007; Barbato et al., 2018).

The results obtained from our study are higher than those found in the Nili-Ravi breed, performed in the period 24th - 35th day of gestation, when the levels of PAGs in both serum and milk

have early peak values. Arshad et al. (2022) reported sensitivity (77.9 vs 89.7 vs 93.3%), specificity (84.2 vs 87.7 vs 93.9%) and accuracy (82.1 vs 88.4 vs 93.7 %) by ELISA test in serum on the 24th, 28th and 35th day after insemination. Results for the milk PAG test were similar, namely sensitivity (77.6 vs. 89.5 vs. 95.0%), specificity (89.1 vs. 91.9, vs. 93.9%), and accuracy (85.1 vs. 91.1 vs. 94.3%). Similar results to ours were reported by Barbato et al. (2017) and Barile et al. (2021) for PAG in serum on day 28 after artificial insemination, respectively accuracy (99%), sensitivity (98%) and specificity (100%) determined by RIA-860. The opinion that the PAG ELISA test in milk is an accurate and effective method for the diagnosis of early pregnancy, similar to the blood PAG ELISA test (Roseline et al., 2021), is confirmed.

Conclusion

Rapid P4 tests and determination of serum progesterone can be used to identify non-pregnant animals after insemination. PAG ELISA tests have high efficiency and are preferable to other methods for diagnosing early pregnancy in buffalo cows.

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